

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

THE ROLE OF TWIST IN THE LEMNISCATE CORE OF AN ELLIPSOIDAL VORTEX IN THE FORMATION OF THE PHASE SPACE OF THE SECOND KIND AND ITS RELATION TO MASS TRANSPORT CIRCULATION

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Abstract

A new concept of twisted vortex fields is introduced through an interpretation of the transport of matter circulation through the lemniscate core of an ellipsoidal vortex. The first case of the distribution of a stationary, non-twisted equipotential field is analyzed according to the rule of lemniscate separation of the phase spaces of vortex domains in an ellipsoidal vortex. The reason for the emergence of "two-sheeted" conformal planes of vortex fields under the condition of twist is explained. A parallel transport of the circulation of mass transfer along lemniscate strips is considered, characterizing the continuity of sliding flows while preserving the convective envelope (shell) of a closed ellipsoidal vortex. The interrelation between the curvature of the section $R_{\xi\eta}$ of the circulation Γ along a two-dimensional carrier region \mathbf{Z} bounded by the vectors ξ and η with the kernel (core) shape of an ellipsoidal vortex is investigated.

Keywords: ellipsoidal vortex, conformal analysis of fields, vortex dynamics of substance, circulation vector, vortex interactions, curvature of the cross-section, lemniscate core, twisted field / helical field, curvature operator, kernel (core).

1. Introduction

A pencil of circles $\theta = \gamma$ passing through the point $a + ib$ in the W -plane corresponds to a pencil of rectangular (equilateral) hyperbolas $\theta_1 + \theta_2 = \gamma$ passing through the pair of points $\pm(\alpha + i\beta) = \sqrt{a + ib}$ which correspond to an orthogonal family of confocal lemniscates in the \mathbf{Z} -plane [1-2].

Both groups of curves under consideration represent families of orthogonal isotherms, which can be expressed by the following formulas:

$$\lg p_1 p_2 = c \text{ and } \theta_1 + \theta_2 = \gamma \quad (1)$$

If c and γ take values of arithmetic progressions, the division is rectangular; with the same difference of

the progressions it becomes quadratic. The latter case is shown in Fig. 1b.

The same lemniscate of the ω -plane can also be expressed in Cartesian coordinates (under the mapping $z = \sqrt{\omega}$)

$$\frac{1}{2} [\lg\{(x - \alpha)^2 + (y - \beta)^2\} + \lg\{(x + \alpha)^2 + (y + \beta)^2\}] = c \quad (2)$$

$$\arctan \frac{y - \beta}{x - \alpha} + \arctan \frac{y + \beta}{x + \alpha} = \gamma$$

where, when imaginary numbers are substituted into the left-hand side of equation (3), the Laplacian remains unchanged, $\Delta u = 0$.

Fig. 1: Transformation of the distribution of a "stationary" equipotential field into another "curved" field when the lemniscate is rotated by 180° between the two foci [2].

The physical interpretation of this picture is explained by the fact that the lemniscate line passes along the boundary separating the "phase spaces of vortex domains" and represents "isotherms" where the difference between the opposite "phase" spaces remains constant. The lemniscate itself obeys a complex law of circulation.

$$a + ib = i \frac{\Gamma}{2\pi} = \frac{z}{|z|^2} = \frac{i}{2\pi} \sum_{\alpha=1}^N \Gamma_{\alpha} \frac{z - z_{\alpha}}{|z - z_{\alpha}|^2} \quad (3)$$

In two figures (Fig. 1) it can be seen that, depending on how the two "propellers" (the two focal points)

interact with each other, the magnitude of the torque changes. This torque is proportional to the sum or the difference of the two circulations Γ_1 and Γ_2 .

$$M_d = \dot{m}(r_1 C_{1\varphi} - r_2 C_{2\varphi}), \quad \Gamma_1 = 2\pi r_1 C_{1\varphi}, \quad \Gamma_2 = 2\pi r_2 C_{2\varphi}, \quad M_a = \frac{\dot{m}}{2\pi} (\Gamma_1 \pm \Gamma_2), \quad (4)$$

where M_d is the dynamic moment, \dot{m} is the mass flow rate, M_a is the moment determined by the circulations Γ_1 and Γ_2 , $C_{1\varphi}$ and $C_{2\varphi}$ are the tangential velocities.

From Fig. 1a it can be seen that, under the symmetric influence of two “sources” located at the foci, a regular distribution is formed: namely, an orthogonal distribution of the potential, perpendicular to the segment $[A_1A_2]$ between the points A_1 (the center of circulation Γ_1) and A_2 (the center of circulation Γ_2). These points lie at the foci of the lemniscate (and of the ellipse as well).

$$\frac{A_1+A_2}{2} + \sqrt{\left(\frac{A_1+A_2}{2}\right)^2 + 1} = e^c \text{ or } \frac{A_1+A_2}{2} = \frac{e^c - e^{-c}}{2}, \quad (5)$$

where

$$\arccos \frac{A_1-A_2}{2} = c \text{ or } \frac{A_1-A_2}{2} = \cos c \quad (6)$$

It denotes the inclination of the semi-axis or asymptote c . From equation $\zeta = (z + \sqrt{z^2 + 1})$ (7), for $c = 1$, we obtain [2]:

$$z = X + iY = \frac{1}{2}(\zeta + \zeta^{-1}) \quad (8)$$

Hence, for the mapping function (Fig. 1a), we find:

$$\begin{cases} X = \frac{x(x^2+y^2+1)}{(x^2+y^2)} = \frac{1}{2}(\zeta + \zeta^{-1}) \cos \varphi \\ Y = \frac{y(x^2+y^2-1)}{(x^2+y^2)} = \frac{1}{2}(\zeta - \zeta^{-1}) \sin \varphi \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

For $X = a$ and $X = b$, the result of the field interaction is shown in Fig. 1a. For $Y = 0$, we obtain a circle of unit radius (Fig. 3b, the conformal case). From equations (9), we obtain the following:

Fig. 2. Reconstruction of function (64) from [2] from a conformal mapping into three-dimensional space according to the lemniscate law of strips - “flat” vortex filaments of an ellipsoidal vortex. A more detailed description of the lemniscate law is given in Chapter 4 of [2]. The twist of each strip is 180° [2–5].

Here, due to the double inverted shift of the field on the Z -plane by an angle α , the lemniscate plane appears to split into four equivalent sheets. In this case, the principle of inverse mapping in conformal geometry comes into operation. A more detailed discussion can be found in works [2, 3, 5]. The point \mathbf{O} behaves as a special isolated point. The lines passing through this point are perpendicular to each other and slide over one another. On the imaginary axis passing through \mathbf{O} (there

$$\frac{X}{\cos \varphi} = \frac{1}{2}(\zeta + \zeta^{-1}), \frac{Y}{\sin \varphi} = \frac{1}{2}(\zeta - \zeta^{-1}) \quad (10)$$

From this, we obtain a new equation:

$$\frac{1}{4}(\zeta + \zeta^{-1})^2 - \frac{1}{4}(\zeta - \zeta^{-1})^2 = 1 \quad (11)$$

Thus, we have

$$\frac{X^2}{\cos^2 \varphi} - \frac{Y^2}{\sin^2 \varphi} = 1 \quad (12)$$

The straight line $\varphi = \gamma$ passing through the zero point of the ζ -plane corresponds to a hyperbola in the Z -plane. Its semi-axes a and b have the ratio:

$$a^2 + b^2 = \cos^2 \varphi + \sin^2 \varphi = 1, \quad (13)$$

Therefore, the foci are located at the focal points $+1$ and -1 on the OX axis, and γ represents the inclination of the asymptote.

In the second case (Fig. 1b), a different lemniscate interaction between the two points A_1 and A_2 appears. Here we deal with a special “twisted” field formed between two points possessing different spin. In this situation, the field rotates by 45° , and along the axis of the “poles”, passing through the center of the white lines, each loxodromic–lemniscate curve passes. These curves arise from the antisymmetric interaction of two different foci. At the same time, each curve is arranged so that it does not obstruct another line from passing through it freely, as shown in Fig. 2.

are the same special isolated points \mathbf{O}_1 and \mathbf{O}_2 , which characterize those very lines.). If one looks at the plane in Fig. 1b from above, a double parallel independent shift of the lines by 45° becomes visible. One shift is directed to the right on one sheet, while the other is directed to the left on the other sheet. This geometry of rotations does not resemble helical geometry and therefore requires proper consideration.

2. Twisted External Field (Conformal Analysis)

Fig. 3 (Conformal analysis of Fig. 1a - the “regular ellipsoidal field”): a) the potential field; b) its isogonal lines. Here the calculation was performed according to formula (8) [2].

Fig. 4 (Conformal analysis of Fig. 1b — the curved (“twisted”) field): a) its potential field, rotated by an angle of 45° ; b) its isogonal field lines. It is noteworthy that along the axis passing through the center of the poles, its “wings” become visible. From this, the dynamics of matter motion can be observed based on the analysis of the colored domains [2].

The question of the existence of the lemniscate image was studied by Lindemann and Volk [6–8]. However, unlike Lindemann’s work, Volk focused his attention only on the lemniscate itself and its internal structures. Here, we can extend the scope of the analysis by introducing one important formula that expresses a complex mapping (conformal transformation) between the complex variables ζ and z . This formula represents the transition from one complex coordinate system to another and is often used to orthogonalize families of curves or fields:

$$z = (i\zeta - \zeta^{-1})/2. \quad (14)$$

(These functions are directly related to the orthogonalization of superimposed external fields. A more detailed discussion can be found in works [2, 5]).

Above are two figures (Fig. 3 and Fig. 4) showing how significantly the external resultant field can change if the first one is rotated by 45° .

3. On the Role of Sectional Curvature in the Transport of the Circulation Vector

In this section, we consider the role of the sectional curvature $R_{\xi\eta}$ in forming a specific distribution pattern of circulation within the microvortex core (at the tip of the core).

When transitioning from a surface of negative curvature during the detachment of a droplet–microvortex from the core of the main spherical vortex, the angular momentum and the spin of the detached microvortex, together with the circulation vector of the substance within it, are conserved [2, 3, 5].

The role of the sectional curvature $R_{\xi\eta}$ in the transport of the circulation vector can be explained as follows.

Let two mutually perpendicular directions ξ and η , be considered in the core of an ellipsoidal microvortex, defining a small two-dimensional area in the tangent space. The transport of the circulation vector along one direction and then along the other, in the general case, does not coincide with the transport performed in the reverse order. It is precisely this non-coincidence that characterizes the curvature of the region under consideration.

If the flow space is locally flat, then the parallel transport of the circulation vector along a small closed contour does not change its orientation. However, in the presence of sectional curvature, an additional rotation of the vector appears after traversing such a contour. Therefore, sectional curvature determines the extent to which the geometry of the vortex core influences the change in the direction of circulation during its transport.

This statement is expressed through the curvature operator

$$R_{\xi\eta} = -\langle \nabla_\xi \nabla_\eta \xi, \eta \rangle + \langle \nabla_\eta \nabla_\xi \xi, \eta \rangle + \langle \nabla_{[\xi,\eta]} \xi, \eta \rangle, \quad (15)$$

where $[\xi, \eta]$ is the Lie bracket of the vector fields ξ and η , whose restrictions to the vortex cell at z are $\xi(z)$ and $\eta(z)$, respectively.

The scalar product of this expression with η gives the sectional curvature in the plane spanned by ξ and η :

$$R_{\xi\eta} = \langle R(\xi, \eta)\xi, \eta \rangle, \quad (16)$$

here $R(\xi, \eta)$ is the curvature operator (the Riemann tensor), ξ and η are two mutually orthogonal tangent vectors, and $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ denotes the scalar product. It follows that the quantity $R_{\xi\eta}$ represents the measure of deviation of the circulation vector from its initial direction during its successive transport along two independent

directions. In other words, the sectional curvature quantitatively describes the local geometry of the twist of the flow.

For a vortex core, this is particularly important because the transport of circulation occurs not in an arbitrary region but in a domain with a pronounced spiral structure of streamlines. In such a geometry, the sectional curvature determines the coherence of the rotational motion of neighboring layers of the medium. If $R_{\xi\eta}$ preserves its sign and changes smoothly, the transport of circulation remains ordered, and the vortex core maintains a stable structure. However, if the curvature changes abruptly, this leads to a local redistribution of circulation, deformation of trajectories, and a possible loss of stability of the vortex core.

Thus, sectional curvature plays the role of a geometric mechanism that regulates the transport of the circulation vector inside a microvortex. It determines how strongly the transport depends on the shape of the local vortex surface, thereby influencing the stability, ordering, and spatial separation of flows in the core region.

Fig. 5. Longitudinal view of the unfolded cone of the funnel forming the core of an ellipsoidal vortex. It can be seen that the plane passing through the center of the core divides it into two halves [2–4]. Due to such a surface configuration, this structure does not allow two different flows from opposite poles to mix with each other.

4. Dimensionality of the sectional curvature

For a physical interpretation, it is convenient to relate the sectional curvature not to an abstract tensor but to the characteristic radius of twist of the vortex core and the angular velocity of rotation.

If $R_{\xi\eta}$ satisfies condition (16), then after normalizing ξ and η to unit vectors, the sectional quantity has the dimension $[R_{\xi\eta}] = 1/m^2$. That is, it is a quantity of the order $R_{\xi\eta} = 1/a^2$ (17), where a is the characteristic radius of curvature of the vortex surface or the radius of the micro-vortex core. In other words, the smaller the radius of the core, the larger the sectional curvature.

5. Relation Between Sectional Curvature and the Radius of the Vortex Core

If locally the stream surface in the micro-vortex core is assumed to be close to a surface with a radius of curvature a , then the estimate takes the form:

$$R_{\xi\eta} = \pm 1/a^2. \quad (18)$$

The sign depends on the geometry: (i) $R_{\xi\eta} = +1/a^2$ if the structure is locally sphere-like; (ii) $R_{\xi\eta} = -1/a^2$ if the structure is saddle-shaped, hyperbolic; (iii) $R_{\xi\eta} = 0$ if the region is locally flat. For our case, where we are dealing with the detachment of a droplet–microvortex and a surface of negative curvature, it is

Here, the sectional twist during the cross-section plays an important role in the detachment from the core of the ellipsoidal vortex. From Fig. 5, a clear separation of flows according to the law of helical surfaces can be observed, which allows the structure to remain in a stable equilibrium state as long as the vortex core exists. A more detailed description of the core is given in the following works [2, 3, 5]. Thus, such a “formed” closed spiral conical surface (which unites all spiral lines within the funnel) characterizes the formation of a funnel with a core of the shape shown in Fig. 5. This configuration never allows unnecessary interactions between flows located on opposite sides of this spiral–lemniscate–helical surface. This surface differs significantly from the simple helical surface of the Riemann type (see Sections 6.2–6.4 [2]), since it can be seen that the geodesic vortex lines pass freely both along the lines of the external spherical оболочка (shell) and along the spiral lines inside a single cone-core, up to the moment of detachment from the tip of this cone-core.

natural to write the condition for the detachment of matter from the tip of the vortex as follows:

$$R_{\xi\eta} = -1/a^2. \quad (19)$$

This means that it is precisely the saddle geometry that promotes the divergence of nearby trajectories and the separation of a droplet–microvortex from the main core.

6. Relation of $R_{\xi\eta}$ with the circulation Γ and the velocity v_θ

For an axisymmetric vortex, the velocity at a distance r from the axis is usually estimated as:

$$v_\theta = \Gamma/2\pi r. \quad (20)$$

At the boundary of the core, $r \sim a$, then

$$v_\theta = \Gamma/2\pi a. \quad (21)$$

From that we get

$$\Gamma \sim 2\pi a v_\theta. \quad (22)$$

If the radius is expressed in terms of the circulation and the characteristic tangential velocity, we obtain:

$$R_{\xi\eta} \sim 1/a^2 \sim 4\pi^2 v_\theta^2 / \Gamma^2 \quad (23)$$

That is, the sectional curvature can be estimated as follows:

$$R_{\xi\eta} \approx \pm 4\pi^2 v_\theta^2 / \Gamma^2 \quad (24)$$

For a region of negative curvature, we have:

$$R_{\xi\eta} \approx -4\pi^2 v_\theta^2 / \Gamma^2 \quad (25)$$

From equations (20–25) the following interesting conclusions follow: (i) the greater the tangential velocity v_θ , the stronger the local twist and the larger the magnitude of the curvature; (ii) the greater the circulation Γ , the larger the characteristic size of the vortex and the smaller the magnitude of the curvature; (iii) the smaller the core radius a , the more strongly the vortex surfaces are curved.

In other words, sectional curvature indicates **how tightly the vortex core is twisted**.

7. Conclusions

The performed analysis shows that the geometry of lemniscate structures and the conformal mappings associated with them play an important role in describing the distribution of potential and vortex fields. A pencil of circles in the \mathbf{W} -plane passing through a fixed point, under the mapping, generates a family of equilateral hyperbolas in the \mathbf{Z} -plane, which turns out to be orthogonal to the family of confocal lemniscates. These two systems of curves form an orthogonal network of isotherms, allowing the field to be described by harmonic functions satisfying the Laplace equation.

It is shown that the geometry of such lines is directly related to the physical interpretation of vortex processes. The lemniscate acts as a boundary separating the phase regions of the vortex field, where a constant difference of phase potentials is maintained. Within the framework of the complex law of circulation, the field distribution is determined by the interaction of several centers of circulation, which leads to the formation of different field configurations—from a symmetric potential distribution to “twisted” structures arising from the antisymmetric interaction of the foci.

The conformal analysis made it possible to establish a connection between the geometry of the field lines and their physical interpretation. In particular, it is shown that straight lines on the auxiliary plane are mapped into hyperbolas on the physical plane, and their parameters determine the positions of the foci and the inclination of the asymptotes. This makes it possible to describe complex field structures through relatively simple analytical relations.

Special attention is given to the role of sectional curvature in the transport of the circulation vector within the microvortex core. Sectional curvature acts as a geometric characteristic that determines the change in orientation of the circulation vector when it is transported along different directions in the tangent space of the flow. In regions of negative curvature, a natural mechanism arises for the divergence of nearby trajectories, which facilitates the detachment of a droplet–microvortex from the main vortex core.

A relationship has been obtained between the sectional curvature, the radius of the vortex core, the tangential (circumferential) velocity, and the circulation. It is shown that the magnitude of the curvature increases as the core radius decreases and the tangential velocity increases, whereas an increase in circulation leads to an increase in the characteristic scale of the vortex and a corresponding decrease in curvature. Thus, the sectional curvature can be regarded as a quantitative measure of the degree of twist of the vortex core.

In general, the conducted study demonstrates that the use of methods of conformal geometry and curvature analysis makes it possible to obtain a comprehensive understanding of the structure of three-dimensional vortex fields, the mechanism of formation of lemniscate boundaries, and the conditions for the stability of the vortex core. This creates a basis for further research into the dynamics of microvortices, the processes of separation of vortex structures (domains), and their interactions in complex flows.

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